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**PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEMS OF
UKRAINIAN REFUGEES USING THE VISUAL
RESEARCH METHOD: PHOTOVOICE**

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Kateryna Ihnatenko, Shorena Sadzaglishvili. Pragmatic analysis of the problems of Ukrainian refugees using the visual research method: photovoice. In this article, the authors are studying photovoice as a visual method in their work with Ukrainian refugees to analyze the process of adaptation to a new environment in host countries. In this research, 11 Ukrainians aged 25-70 participated in four workshops as part of the research project “The voices of Ukrainian Refugees: When Fleeing the War.” The article aims to present photovoice as a method for understanding the processes and possible participation of Ukrainian refugees in advocacy, examples of work with refugees from Ukraine, and a pragmatic analysis of the pre-collected material. The authors are considering fieldwork examples in Bordeaux (France) with Ukrainian refugees.

Keywords: *photovoice, participation, visual methods, narrative, Ukrainian refugees.*

In the fourth year of the war in Ukraine, society is faced with the need to reflect on social issues of polarity, on the protection of rights, and on the individual personal

processes of refugees using visual methods. A significant problem is that the lack of opportunities for refugees to express their needs makes them invisible and unheard, and their rights insufficiently protected. In this regard, to deeply understand the context of war, continuous integration, and life in displacement and exile and to give refugees a voice and make them visible, we used photovoice in our primary research with Ukrainian refugees.

Photovoice is a research methodology in which individuals, typically those with *little power*, use photographs and/or video to describe their surroundings and experiences, expressing their thoughts and reflections about them. The method is designed to enhance their participation through first-person methodologies, providing an alternative form of expression for those who have difficulty communicating verbally. The photonovel is intended to include new voices in policy debates by facilitating collective learning, expression, and action (Wang, Burris, Xiang, 1996). Photovoice uses photographs to gather information about a focus group or population for research, education, advocacy, or healing. Participants take pictures and bring them to the group for discussion. After discussing the picture, participants describe or create narratives or stories describing why they took it. The group can categorize and display the photographs for community education or advocacy.

Photovoice is based on qualitative research and is aligned with the *hermeneutic paradigm*, which seeks to understand complex human phenomena (Simó, 2022). At the same time, Tsang K. (2020) argues that photovoice data needs to be used in critical, *phenomenological approaches*, and beyond. The first approach is *crucial* because different thoughts of critical theory inform it. As a research method, especially as a phenomenological research method, photovoice has certain advantages for studying social phenomena compared to other methods, such as interviews. First, interviews may not accurately reflect the meaningful lived experiences of participants as they are typically influenced by the researcher's agenda and assumptions (Brunsden, Goatcher, 2007).

In contrast, photovoice allows participants to decide what and how to present and express their thoughts, views, and feelings throughout the research process (Asaba et al., 2014). Thus, photovoice allows the researcher to capture the meaningful lived experiences of the participants regarding the phenomenon (Plunkett et al., 2013). Second, traditional interview methods rely heavily on narratives and words. However, as (Kirova, Emme, 2006) argued, many layers of lived experience cannot be easily expressed and interpreted by narratives and words. Visual images such as photographs can be a valuable tool for participants to create more profound meanings of the world as they can encourage them to reflect, remember, and imagine feelings, thoughts, events, and other issues at a given moment (Glaw, Kable, Hazelton, 2017). In this sense, photovoice may be a better method for social research.

Other visual research methods include collages, photographs, drawings, mapping, diagrams, collages, and objects - all of which can be created by the research participants or presented by the researcher as a hint. Collage is one of the photovoice modalities that involves narrative collage – a term borrowed from painting and modernist poetry. In cognitive studies, narrative tends to be associated with sense-making and problem-solving activities.

We started from the hypothesis that Ukrainian refugees abroad live between two realities, which hinders their integration into host societies and creates additional difficulties. “Ukrainians do not cut ties with Ukraine, existing between two social realities without being securely anchored in either of the two” (Gorbach, Polshchykova, Ryabchuk, 2024). This was traced through work with narratives while interpreting photos on the topic of “my identity and who am I?”.

The following hypothesis is that the trajectories of refugees differ and depend on gender, class, and role. The third meeting is devoted to the topic of “host society” to study narratives for further understanding of how the integration process and the difficulties associated with it occur against the background of what psychological state all processes occur in - the creation of a new identity, integration, and common trajectories-intentions.

How is this connection maintained, and through what communication channels - visible or invisible, such as images, traditions, and language?

The qualitative study employs a methodological design rooted in a narrative-in-action approach (Bruner, 1990; Ricouer, 1984). due to its focus on understanding individuals' experiences, which Salvador Simo interpreted in "Introduction to Photovoice Research Technique" (2022). Thus, we used three data collection methods to understand the lived experience of refugees in the conception of identity, integration, and adoption from a variety of angles and sources. First, we interviewed random Ukrainian refugees (N=3) living in France (Bordeaux, France). Second, using participant observation, we joined some of the activities, that were provided by the Association in Bordeaux "La Maison Ukrainienne", including manifestation timed to 3d year of russia's invasion in Ukraine, to a film conference "Vasyl Stus: resistance artistic as intellectual", and demonstration a film "Prohibited", a linguistic café, and observing documentary film "A Gentle Force". Shake up Europe". Finally, we used photovoice to provide four workshops for Ukrainian refugees (N=13) in Bordeaux and distance participating Ukrainian refugees (N=5) from Germany, Poland, the United Kingdom, and Georgia. In this article, we will focus only on the challenges that follow the photovoice process of Ukrainian refugees. In our research, we presented not only the "voice" or word but also the picture as material that can and should be worked with to obtain more objective material and a method through which one can create, that is, change the situation. These photovoice workshops use photographic documentation of Ukrainian refugees as a tool to record and reflect on their needs, facilitate dialogue, encourage action, and study their intentions for the future.

Several vital ideas emerge when considering this question using the Photovoice, a participatory research method.

1. Amplifying Voices through Visual Narratives

Photovoice empowers individuals to share their experiences through photography. This method allows them to document their journey, highlighting their unique barriers, from accessibility issues to inadequate healthcare. These visual narratives serve as

powerful tools to raise awareness among policymakers and humanitarian organizations about the specific needs of refugees with disabilities.

2. Capturing lived experiences

Amid the ongoing military conflict in Ukraine and facing multiple losses, psychological trauma, and social polarization, Ukrainian refugees remain much more vulnerable.

3. Developing empathy and understanding

For viewers, Photovoice opens a window into the lived experiences of refugees, promoting empathy and a deeper understanding of their plight. These images can challenge preconceived notions and highlight the importance of inclusive support systems.

4. Participants tended to avoid topics related to traumatic events.

Despite their reluctance to discuss the war, the subject was still discussed, even though it was not explicitly included and highlighted in any workshop. Commonly raised issues included the onset of the full-scale invasion, memories of evacuation, decisions to leave the country, and experiences of staying in basements or shelters during the initial days of the invasion and bombings. In the context of reconciliation within Ukrainian society, participants expressed concerns about how those who remained would perceive and understand those who have left.

Photographs can express more words or in a different way, photographs cannot speak about themselves. *A pragmatic analysis* is crucial, especially in the context of the researcher's fieldwork. The focus is on understanding the purpose and the effect a text should have on its reader: how it influences the perception of information and what emotions it evokes. In this regard, the visual communication channels play a significant role in shaping the emotional impact of "communicational" messages. However, specifically within the context of visual research methods, a pragmatic analysis allows for a deeper understanding of how messages are received and interpreted through images, which can be particularly powerful in environments where emotions and perceptions are highly influenced by visual cues.

Following the *pragmatic approach*, we analyzed the most dynamic moments, how to conduct photovoice, the specific contacts between facilitator and participants, and the features of communicative narratives from other parties involved in promoting information about events. From the perspective of analysing insights from participants using a set of linguistic and logistical tools, we developed accounts of discursive social and participative interaction (Duffy, 2008).

The workshop structure of the photovoice sessions contained four meetings. (1) Introductory Meeting: we began by introducing ourselves and providing an overview of the photovoice concept. Participants' expectations were gathered during this session, and tasks were assigned to be completed before the next meeting. (2) In the second meeting, participants shared photographs they had taken. They offered their interpretations of these images, reflecting on the themes of "My Identity" (who I am? My nationality? Religious? Hobby?) and "Health" (mental and physical). (3) Third meeting – the focus of this session is the topic "Host Country/Society: pros and cons," where a deeper understanding of the integration process and the challenges that participants face was delved into. (4) The Fourth Meeting, "Trajectories: the path of Ukrainian refugees in France" (rights and social inclusion), marks the final session, where participants reflect on the journey, discussing what was most valuable, what participants have learned, and what they are taking away from the experience.

Initial meetings were confrontational, with numerous questions resembling an interrogation. Following debriefings, adjustments were made to the instructions, announcements, and the facilitator's presentation. An interest in photography served as a motivating and stable factor for participation in photovoice. Initially, there was significant engagement and views on the NGO's Telegram channel, which was used to promote the photovoice project in Bordeaux; however, actual attendance at workshops was relatively low. Building trust with the facilitator and maintaining a consistent meeting schedule (four sessions) proved crucial. For example, Ukrainians were more likely to accept a facilitator who belonged to them on nationality, experience, etc. Participants who attended at least two meetings demonstrated better awareness and a willingness to

continue participating, which is attributed to the instructions and clarifications they received.

In this article, we propose a strategy for conducting photovoice that consists of four stages: a pre-study analysis based on the researcher's interpretations of the refugees' situation context to identify potential challenges; gathering and examining preliminary data of the main study; and photograph presentations based on the participants' interpretations and theorization.

1. Developing a theme for the photo assignment. This stage provides an opportunity for participants to collectively discuss and decide on the theme for the photo assignment.

2. Discuss the project and review the assignment. The project and assignment are reviewed at this stage, focusing on ethical considerations. It is essential to determine the ownership of the photographs and clarify how they will be shared.

3. Photograph shooting. Participants are given one week to create photographs based on the photo assignment.

4. Group discussion. Participants meet as a group to critically reflect on and discuss their photographs. They examine the meaning behind each image and the issues it raises and explore potential solutions or changes that could be made to address these issues. We did not dive into the data analysis because that was not the purpose of this article.

To summarize, the proposed strategy involves pragmatic analysis and encourages the researcher to analyze the pre-data based on his or her interpretations and those of participants. A preliminary analysis is crucial at this initial stage, allowing us to conclude that specific processes occur within the Ukrainian refugee community. These processes have both external and internal origins.

Externally, refugees may fear or distrust; internally, their traumatic experiences may limit or even prevent participants from speaking about their emotions, feelings, and experiences, especially when these are linked to triggering photographs or, conversely. Additionally, there is often an underestimation of refugees' influence and significance in discussions around shifting responsibilities. This stage's purpose is to create a "dialogue"

between the researcher's interpretation and participants to develop an integrative explanation of the phenomenon of Ukrainian refugees (Tsang, 2020).

Photovoice, as a developing and emerging visual method, has received increasing attention in various fields of the social sciences over the last decade. As mentioned above, researchers encounter different methodological challenges when conducting photovoice research (Tsang, 2020). One of the challenges highlighted here is to analyze both visual data (participants' voices) and narrative data (interview data) and encourage the researcher to analyze the data based on a pragmatic analysis. Thus, this work can help further utilize the participants' photographs and narratives and the researcher's narratives to understand a phenomenon, generating a more credible visual and narrative representation and explanation of the phenomenon.

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